

Deliverable 8.1 Communication Kit

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0.3	Tiziana Lombardo (Net7), Jan Wiebelitz (LUH)	Review

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1.0	Sona Arasteh, Léa Foumany	Final version
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List of Acronyms

CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESS	Earth System Science
JUST	Judicious, Unbiased, Safe and Transparent
LUMEN	Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network
MD	Molecular Dynamics
NGO	Non-governmental Organisation
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities

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1. Introduction

This document serves as the communication toolkit for the LUMEN project (Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Network). It defines the project's identity and details how it is communicated through key facts, messages, and visual elements. Additionally, it includes resources like logos and templates designed to support communication and dissemination activities throughout the project's duration. This document also serves as a style guide for all consortium members.

The materials included in the Communication Kit are partially customisable – some can be tailored to meet specific communication or dissemination needs and formats (e.g., various social media posts, flyers, and PowerPoint templates). The materials are available under an open licence, typically the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence (CC-BY).

The LUMEN Communication Kit aligns with the [Communication Kit](#) (Rabar et al. 2025) published by the [GRAPHIA project](#), mirroring the collaboration between the projects and ensuring that all communication and dissemination efforts can be easily harmonised (e.g. for collaboratively organised events).

As the project progresses, the Communication Kit is expected to expand, incorporating new items in response to emerging needs.

2. LUMEN project identity

To support transparent, clear, and effective communication about the LUMEN project, partners are provided with a set of key facts, a project description template, along with a brief description of the project's identity rooted in Open Science values and stakeholder-tailored messaging. This helps to maintain consistency across the consortium and provides a solid foundation for translating content when partners wish to share information about the project in their respective languages.

2.1 Key Facts

Project acronym	LUMEN
Project full title	Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Network
Project start & end date	1 January 2025 - 31 December 2027
Funding	Horizon Europe
Call framework	HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01

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Geographical scope	ERA
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Table 1: LUMEN Key Facts

2.2 Project Description

The LUMEN project is an initiative to advance cross-domain collaboration and discovery processes in four academic fields: Mathematics (Maths), Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), Earth System Science (ESS), and Molecular Dynamics (MD). Through interdisciplinary solutions spanning all four domains, LUMEN sets out to significantly improve discovery by innovation, simplifying initial research phases and facilitating access to advanced AI-powered tools for researchers. LUMEN aims to transform and strengthen EOSC services by promoting innovative and customisable solutions for data discovery. LUMEN thereby seeks to attract new users while simultaneously fostering Open Science principles.

By expanding existing discovery platforms in the SSH (GoTriple) and Maths (Centre Mersenne) domains and developing new platforms for the two other domains, the project will deploy a set of interoperable platforms. These will include cross-platform features as well as domain-specific tools tailored to the needs of researchers. Eventually, this set of interconnected and interoperable platforms will work as a fully operational multidisciplinary ecosystem of discovery platforms, enabling seamless cross-disciplinary knowledge exchange and collaboration.

2.3 LUMEN Slogan & Tagline

The main slogan used for LUMEN is: “Discovering knowledge across domains”. This slogan expresses LUMEN’s mission as a cross-disciplinary project focused on fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange among the four key disciplines within the project. The tagline “Science thrives through collaboration” complements the main project slogan. This tagline reinforces LUMEN’s core message that meaningful scientific progress emerges through collective effort and shared expertise.

The main slogan is featured prominently on the website header and homepage, as well as in presentation decks and branded materials such as flyers, banners, and merchandise. The supportive tagline is used to reinforce this message across secondary communication channels, including social media and external communications, helping to build a cohesive narrative around LUMEN.

2.4 Core Values

LUMEN’s project identity is shaped through its commitment to the principles and values of Open Science. This commitment is expressed in how LUMEN outputs contribute to their advancement.

Core Value	LUMEN Talking Point
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Diversity	LUMEN promotes diversity as a guiding principle. Through multilingual services and inclusive practices, LUMEN ensures that a wide range of disciplines, identities, and perspectives help shape the project outputs.
Collaboration	By building a network of interconnected platforms for different scientific communities, LUMEN enables knowledge sharing and trans-disciplinary collaboration. Through co-design and user-oriented development, LUMEN builds resilient services that support integration with the EOSC.
Equity	LUMEN strives to help everyone benefit from scientific research, regardless of their linguistic, cultural, gender, academic, geographical, organisational, and/or economic background. By supporting multilingualism and increasing the discoverability of research and research outputs, LUMEN empowers stakeholders both inside and beyond academia. LUMEN approaches data with the appropriate care and recognises that their context, consent and representation are essential to the ethical use of data. To this end, the FAIR semantic platform developed by LUMEN will integrate standardised JUST data annotation practices.
Inclusiveness	LUMEN is committed to creating discovery solutions that reflect the diverse needs of scientific and societal communities. By emphasising co-design and working collaboratively with users from different disciplines, sectors, and backgrounds, we ensure that LUMEN services are not only accessible but also relevant for all.
Accessibility	LUMEN builds discovery services that make it easy for all researchers to find and work with scientific outputs across disciplines and needs. By embedding accessibility, adaptability, and user-driven design from the start, we ensure that if an output is not accessible, it is not yet finished.
Openness	Through all of its outputs, LUMEN is committed to the value of openness. Beyond transparent development, this includes enhancing the discoverability and visibility of research outputs, enhancing access to research metadata and enabling interdisciplinary collaboration. FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) principles are at the heart of LUMEN, with the FAIR Semantic Management Space facilitating FAIRification and enhancing interoperability among existing tools.

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Table 2: LUMEN core values and talking points

2.5 Stakeholder-tailored messages & taglines

The stakeholder-tailored messages and taglines listed below serve to facilitate communication and dissemination activities for all consortium members.

Stakeholder	Message	Tagline
Research infrastructures	LUMEN enhances collaboration among research communities, accelerates progress, and simplifies the uptake of research results, driving innovation forward.	Facilitating collaboration, advancing research, Enabling Innovation.
Research communities	LUMEN enhances collaboration among research communities, enabling faster and simplified uptake of research findings.	Shared expertise for better science.
Individual researchers	LUMEN simplifies access to research, boosting visibility and facilitating broader impact.	Simplifying access, amplifying visibility in research
EOSC	LUMEN enriches the EOSC ecosystem of services, supports the EOSC Innovation Centre, and aligns seamlessly with EOSC-related projects.	Bridging Projects for the Future of EOSC
SMEs and private companies	LUMEN enables access to experts and trusted data.	Smarter, faster innovation through accessible scientific expertise
Policymakers	LUMEN enables access to experts, trusted data and increases trust in Science.	Fostering trust through Open Science
NGOs	LUMEN connects NGOs with reliable data and research insights to support informed action and social change.	Build a better world with trusted data.
Data providers	LUMEN improves (meta)data quality, JUST data annotation and FAIRness,	Enhancing (meta)data quality through FAIR and JUST annotation

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	software platform for data providers to present analyses on the quality and FAIR compliance of their data sources.	
Media	Through fostering cross-disciplinarity LUMEN provides media with usage data. The ecosystem of platforms serves as a multiplier channel.	Trustworthy data for stories you can tell.
Citizens	LUMEN enables trusted data.	Knowledge society can rely on.

Table 3: LUMEN stakeholder-tailored messages and taglines

3. Visual Identity

3.1 Logo Usage/Branding Elements

The project logo is the basic element of LUMEN's visual identity. It is applied in all visual project material and outcomes (fact sheets, presentations, posters, website) in order to ensure consistent branding across all communication tools. As LUMEN will onboard new scientific communities into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the project logo has been developed in a co-branding effort with the EOSC to highlight the close collaboration. The logo includes an icon, the project name, as well as the EOSC favicon. The [co-branding guidelines for EOSC INFRAEOSC projects](#) serve as a guide to how LUMEN's visual identity will be employed throughout the project.

The logo is provided in colour and black/white versions, in both horizontal and vertical orientations for multiple uses and accessibility. In the logo, the project name is spelt "Lumen", in text, the project name is spelt LUMEN.

Fig. 1: LUMEN Logos in horizontal, vertical, in full colour and bichrom.

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Furthermore, a favicon has been created to support LUMEN's social media presence:

Fig. 2: LUMEN Favicon

The three official brand colours presented in the LUMEN visual identity are:

Neptune
HEX: #75b6b2
RGB: 117/182/178
CMYK: 36/0/2/29

Warm Black
HEX: #040204
RGB: 4/3/5
CMYK: 90/80/60/95

Orange
HEX: #ee7444
RGB: 238/116/68
CMYK: 0/65/75/0 3.2

Fig. 3: LUMEN colours

3.2 Fonts

LUMEN uses two main fonts: Quicksand Light and Roboto Regular. Both fonts are open source fonts. Quicksand is a display sans serif with rounded terminals. Roboto is a sans serif typeface as well. Both fonts convey a modern-simplistic feeling and are easy to read. LUMEN uses Quicksand for titles and headings, Roboto for body text and captions.

3.3 Templates

WP8 has prepared a set of templates to ensure a coherent visual identity as well as compliance with the project brand identity and EC requirements. These include templates for deliverables, Milestones, PowerPoint presentations, and social media posts tailored to specific campaigns. Templates are shared and accessible to LUMEN consortium through the dedicated internal shared folder.

Deliverable X.X	
Title of Deliverable	
Authors	
Submission Date	xx.xx.20xx
Due Date	xx.xx.20xx
Lead beneficiary	
Corresponding WP	
Deliverable Identifier	DX.X
Type	e.g Report, Other, to be filled out according to GA
Dissemination Level	to be filled out according to GA
DOI	
Project Title	Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network
Project Acronym	LUMEN
Project No.	101187940

Fig. 4: LUMEN deliverable template

Fig. 5: LUMEN presentation template

Fig. 6: Example social media for communication campaign “LUMEN Voices”

4. Communication Guidelines & Policies

4.1 General Guidelines

All communication and dissemination activities conducted on behalf of LUMEN must take into account the following:

- compliance with the project identity

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- compliance with the LUMEN visual identity
- compliance with EC requirements (see chapter 5 “Compliance and Accessibility”)
- accessibility requirements
- target audience (e.g. stakeholders, scientific communities)

4.2 Social Media

4.2.1 Purpose and Objectives

Social media channels serve as useful tools for enhancing communication and engagement in LUMEN by promoting transparency, engagement, and visibility. Their primary purpose is to share updates, milestones, outcomes, events and relevant information with stakeholders, partners, and the broader public in a timely and accessible way. The project has created three social media accounts on [Bluesky](#) (@lumen-eu.bsky.social), [LinkedIn](#), and [YouTube](#) (managed by OPERAS).

4.2.2 Look & Feel

All social media communication should reflect LUMEN’s values and objectives in a manner that is professional, approachable, and inclusive. Partners are encouraged to use the approved visual assets – including logos, fonts, and templates – to ensure a cohesive and recognisable presence. Standardised visual templates (see 3.3) have been made available to all project partners and should be used consistently across all platforms to maintain a unified look and feel.

The following style guidelines should be followed:

- **Tone:** Friendly yet professional. Avoid overly technical language where possible – keep it accessible to a wider audience.
- **Language:** Use British English consistently across all posts when posting in English. Project partners are advised to use tools such as Grammarly.
- **Clarity:** Keep messages concise and clear. Avoid abbreviations that may not be widely understood. Avoid overly technical language where possible – keep it accessible to a non-specialist audience.
- **Inclusivity:** Use language that is respectful and inclusive of all audiences.

4.2.3 Content

Effective social media content should inform, engage, and inspire action while aligning with LUMEN’s mission and target audience. Social Media messaging should always communicate the impact and relevance of the project. Suggested types of content include:

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- Project Updates: Share milestones, deliverables, activities, and achievements from different work packages.
- Scientific domains: How LUMEN integrates the four scientific domains.
- Event Promotion: Promote upcoming webinars, workshops, or conferences, and encourage participation.
- Knowledge Sharing: Break down complex concepts related to LUMEN into simple, understandable and shareable facts.
- Behind-the-Scenes: Offer insights into WP meetings or collaborative efforts.

Project partners are encouraged to vary content formats to keep engagement high. To better engage local stakeholders, partners are encouraged to translate posts into their local languages and adapt the messaging to reflect local priorities.

4.2.4 Hashtags & Tags

Project partners are encouraged to tag institutions and organisations involved in the planning of events or the development of outputs when disseminating information on social media.

LUMEN core hashtags: #LUMEN4Openness, #LUMENConnect

Contextual Hashtags: #OpenScience, #OpenData, #OpenResearch, #OpenSource, #discovery, #collaboration

Hashtags for scientific communities:

- ESS: #SustainableScience
- SSH: #multilingualism
- MD: #ResearchInMotion
- Maths: #OpenMaths

4.3. Website

The project has created a website under the domain <https://lumenproject.eu/>. The LUMEN website serves as a central platform for dissemination and communication activities. All project outcomes, activities, collaborations and events are published there. To engage more effectively with the audience, a newsletter has also been created, which users can subscribe to via the website. It also connects users to the project's social media channels and offers a newsletter subscription to encourage communication and engagement with the wider public. In addition, a Zenodo community is being integrated to ensure open access to project outputs.

As the project progresses, the website's structure will be gradually expanded and reorganised with additional categories as well as content on developments, offering insights, and effectively promoting key exploitable results. WP8 relies on the cooperation and input of all project partners to fill the website with relevant content. The website is hosted on WordPress and was developed in collaboration with B2 Atelier de Design. A screenshot of the website can be seen in the figure below.

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Fig. 7: Screenshot of the LUMEN website

4.4. Printed Materials

For certain events, the production of printed materials may be required, such as flyers, rollups, posters for third-party events and the final event. These materials will be prepared and printed as needed. When producing printed materials, project partners are encouraged to prioritise the use of recycled and recyclable resources wherever possible.

4.5. Crisis management

To address negative comments, misinformation, or reputational risks, the following procedure should be followed by project partners:

1. Notify the WP8 Leader as well as the project coordination office (PCO).
2. Any concerns should be reported as outlined above so that WP8 can internally discuss the most appropriate course of action, depending on the specific circumstances, prior to issuing any response.
3. WP8 will advise on the nature of the response, if a response is necessary.

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5. Compliance and Accessibility

5.1 EC Guidelines

All communication materials – including social media posts, flyers, presentations, brochures, posters and similar – must adhere to the following EC communication requirements:

- **Funding Acknowledgement:** Display the “Funded by the European Union” - emblem on all materials, as shown in the figure below.
- **Disclaimers:** Where opinions or interpretations are expressed, include the appropriate disclaimer to clarify that these do not necessarily reflect the views of the EU.
- **Data Protection:** Ensure full compliance with data protection regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). No sensitive data is to be shared publicly without explicit consent.
- **Neutrality:** Avoid content that may be interpreted as politically biased or controversial, particularly in a way that could appear to represent the views of the project or the EU funding body.

Work Package 8 has made the official “Funded by EU” emblem as well as the appropriate disclaimer text available to all project partners. In addition, all project partners are strongly encouraged to familiarise themselves with the [official EU communication guidelines](#) to ensure full compliance.

5.2 Zenodo community

The LUMEN project runs until the end of 2027. To enhance the disseminability of suitable project results, a dedicated [Zenodo community](#) has been established. Additionally, the LUMEN Zenodo community serves as a means for archiving project results and ensuring their sustainability.

5.3 Accessibility

All social media and digital content should be designed to be as inclusive and accessible as possible, ensuring that individuals with disabilities can fully engage with the project's materials.

- **Key practices include:**
- **Alternative Text for Images:** Whenever possible, include meaningful alt text that describes the content and purpose of images, enabling users who rely on screen readers to understand the visuals.
- **Visual Design Considerations:** Ensure that any text within images has sufficient colour contrast and is set in a clear, legible font size to accommodate users with visual impairments.

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- Captions and Transcripts: Video content should include captions, and transcripts should be provided for spoken elements where feasible.
- Plain Language: Avoid overly technical language. Where possible, include a simplified summary to make content more accessible to a wider audience.

6. Conclusion

This Communication Kit is designed to provide the tools, messaging framework, and overall guidelines to effectively engage with the target audience of LUMEN and support the project's objectives. Using the resources and following the guidelines outlined in this document ensures consistency, clarity and alignment with LUMEN values.

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7. References

Rabar, U., Dubber, A., Silver, C., Fletcher, K.-A. & Lombardo, Tiziana (2025): GRAPHIA deliverable 6.1 Communication Kit. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14945633>.

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